

UTILIZATION OF SOLAR ENERGY FOR ADEQUATE POWER SUPPLY AND NOISE REDUCTION FROM CONVENTIONAL GENERATORS IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.

***¹Agori John Ebipukebina, ²Okoroafor Solomon Ugwa, ¹Oba Jeff and ¹Umeadi Kester**

**¹Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Oleh Campus, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria.*

²Department of Civil Engineering, Michael Opara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20052376>

Keywords:

Noise, Solar Energy, Generators, Solar Panels, Solar Photovoltaic (PV) Modules.

Abstract: *The use of fossil fuel powered generators in homes and public institutions is as a result of epileptic power supply in Nigeria. Generators are noisy with high decibel levels. The noise in learning institutions is a significant issue impacting student concentration, health, overall wellbeing, psychology and the overall learning environment. Noise from these generators can reach up to 110 dB(A) and sometimes higher, leading to a need for mitigation measures like careful placement, acoustic barriers, proper generator selection with low noise emissions and to think of alternative sources of power. Sunlight is a form of radiant energy that travels to the earth as electromagnetic waves. In reality, the light we see is just a small part of the energy we receive from the Sun. The radiant energy from the Sun covers the full breadth of the electromagnetic spectrum. Using solar technology, we are able to "capture" the Sun's radiant energy and convert it to either heat or electricity. This sun is captured using solar panel, which is a set of solar photovoltaic (PV) modules electrically connected and mounted on a supporting structure. The study was conducted in the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Oleh Campus, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. The noise level produced from three generators in the block housing the department were measured using a sound meter and the combined noise level from the sources to a classroom was found to be 41.72dB. The equipment and power ratings of the equipment in the department were evaluated and the power need of the department was 5,157Watt Hr/Day. These value was used to calculate the solar power components that will effectively power the*

***Agori John Ebipukebina, Okoroafor Solomon Ugwa, Oba Jeff and Umeadi Kester**

department and reduce noise. The solar components needed were 12 numbers 600W Solar panel, 4 numbers 12.0 volts batteries, 1 number 5000W inverter, charge control cables and connectors and were installed. Using solar power to replace or supplement diesel generators in universities provides a silent, clean energy source that eliminates the high-decibel noise pollution, fumes, and vibration associated with traditional power generation. Implementing solar systems (photovoltaic panels, inverters, and battery storage) directly reduces the reliance on noisy, fuel dependent generators, creating a quieter, more conducive environment for learning and research, improves energy sustainability, drastically reduce the operational and it is environmentally friendly.

Introduction

Education is the cradle of development and must be properly guarded. Higher institutions are citadels of learning engaging in high intellectual discourse that require quiet ambience. The high noise level in Nigeria's institutions of higher learning has become a growing concern (Agbo, 2020). In many universities, particularly in regions with unreliable power supply, generators serve as a primary source of electricity. Generator noise in educational institutions, often ranging from 50 dB(A) to 110 dB(A) due to reliance on backup power (Olamijulo, 2016), severely disrupts learning by masking speech, reducing concentration, and hindering cognitive tasks. It causes significant health issues, including fatigue, headache, tinnitus, and elevated stress, while lowering academic performance and teaching effectiveness. There has been increasing interest in solar convertors, mostly for energy. It is globally acclaimed that academic

achievement of students is predetermined by the efforts put into the learning process by individuals to comprehend learning activities presented to them in the course of their study. In order to achieve high academic standard in schools, researchers have advocated for ways of improving the learning environment for both teachers and students. One of the ways is to improve the lighting systems and to reduce noise so as to enable students and teachers to work into long hours without hitches or stress in order to clear a backlog of work (Iorbee et al., 2017). The School administrators have resorted to the use of standby generators to power their classrooms, laboratories and other school facilities. However, in the depressed economy like Nigeria, fueling of generators is cost intensive, it causes noise pollution and also poses serious health consequences. This has recently amplified the call for solar energy system which is fuel free and cost effective for use in school environments. Solar energy system

***Agori John Ebipukebina, Okoroafor Solomon Ugwa, Oba Jeff and Umeadi Kester**

is an efficient method of providing illumination and electrical energy for better visibility and operations of electrical utilities which improves learning and healthy leaving conditions in schools and homes and eliminates noise associated with generators. It is a photovoltaic (PV) module that collects energy from the sun and stores it in batteries to operate the required wattage of light and other related electrical gadgets connected to the system (Smith, Radestsky and Yue, 2010). This is generally used for energy savings, cost savings, and environmental reasons. This system is called grid free or stand-alone meaning that it can generate its own electricity at a specific site. Civil Engineering Department, along with other faculties within a one-storey building, relies on these generators for day-to-day operations. However, the use of generators is often accompanied by significant noise pollution and environmental concerns, adversely affecting the learning environment and the overall well-being of students and staff. There has been a growing incidence of noise pollution within the tertiary institutions in Nigeria, despite the institutions' position as citadels of knowledge and intellectual discourse. Interestingly though schools, hospitals and government reserved areas are designated as noise control zones, whereby the noise levels must not exceed that stipulated in Nigeria's National Environmental (Noise Standards and Control) Regulations, 2009 (NESREA, 2007), that has not been the case.

An ideal educational setting should be serene and conducive for both learning and working. However, due to the erratic power supply in

Nigeria coupled with increase in number of commercial outfits, there has been an upsurge in the proliferation of portable generators at institutional settings (Olamijulo, 2016). Studies conducted on noise from portable generators and its effects on human health in institutional environment are sparse. Noise levels from exposure to portable generators and its perceived attendant effects was assessed in this study. Oladele Ajose building (OAB) was purposively selected for this pilot study based on the frequency of generator use and level of commercial activities. A semi structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from staff and students. Noise levels in decibels (dB) was measured in six selected location for eight weeks in the indoor and outdoor environment of the building, using a calibrated AEMC sound meter. Results were compared with WHO guideline limits. Mean noise level in the indoor and outdoor environment was 60.26 ± 8.45 dB and 58.15 ± 4.53 dB respectively. Despite their convenience, diesel generators produce high levels of noise and emissions, which can lead to health issues and decreased productivity (Chen et al., 2022a). The reliance on fossil fuels for power generation is increasingly being scrutinized, prompting a shift toward renewable energy sources. Solar energy presents a viable alternative, offering a cleaner, quieter, and more sustainable power solution. By replacing traditional generators with solar power systems, universities can effectively reduce noise pollution while also lowering carbon emissions (Ghaffarian Hoseini et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2022). Transitioning to solar-powered systems not only aligns with global

sustainability goals but also enhances operational reliability, as solar energy can provide continuous power during daylight hours without the noise and air pollution associated with generators. This project aims to explore strategies for mitigating generator noise and integrating solar-powered lighting as a sustainable alternative.

1.1 Noise

Noise is an unwelcomed artificial sound that pervades the surroundings. It is any sound that irritates one's ear and comes from an outside source. On the other hand, noise pollution consists of annoying or harmful noise (Camarillo et al., 2021). There are three major categories of noise sources associated with facilities, these are:

- i. Musical Instruments. Example: Guitar, drum, piano, flute.
- ii. Human Voice. Produced by the vibration of vocal cords.
- iii. Vehicles. Example: Car engines, horns, sirens.
- iv. Animals. Example: Dogs barking, birds chirping, cows mooing.
- v. Generators

In schools, there are places that noises are inevitable especially in classrooms and even in library that strictly implemented a silence environment occupied by students. The American Speech Language-Hearing Association suggests that the most appropriate noise level for learning should be in the range of 30 to 40 dB for an empty classroom in which there is no student, and should not exceed 50 dB for a classroom containing students (Bulunuz, 2014). The study was anchored on the

assumption that cognitive performances of students can be affected by many factors in the learning environment (Diacó, 2014). Additionally, this study evaluated the impact of noise pollution in the learning environment on student-participants' cognitive performances, assessed the intensity of background noises in their classrooms and homes, and identified the primary sources of the noises.

1.1.1 Effect of Noise

Noise in a learning environment negatively impacts students by impairing their concentration, cognitive abilities like memory and reading comprehension, and communication with teachers. Excessive noise can also lead to behavioral issues, reduced motivation, fatigue, and increased anxiety. These could be classified as:

a. Cognitive and academic effects

- i. Impaired concentration and memory: Noise makes it harder for students to focus on lessons, retain information, and perform tasks requiring short-term memory.
- ii. Reduced reading and language skills: Background noise can disrupt speech perception, making it difficult for children to understand what is being said and learn language-related skills like reading.
- iii. Decreased academic performance: Noise is linked to lower academic achievement, as it hinders a student's capacity to learn, comprehend, and perform well on tests.
- iv. Problem-solving difficulties: Noise can interfere with executive functions, which are essential for problem-solving and other cognitive tasks.

b. Psychological and emotional effects

- i. Increased stress and anxiety: Continuous noise acts as a chronic stressor, leading to feelings of annoyance and anxiety in students.
- ii. Reduced motivation: Frustration from a noisy environment can lead to a loss of motivation for learning.
- iii. Fatigue: Students may experience greater fatigue at the end of the school day because their brains work harder to process information in a noisy setting.

1.1.2 Noise Detector

A sound level meter is a noise detector that comprises a microphone, a preamplifier, signal processing, and a display. The microphone converts the sound signal to an equivalent electrical signal. The most suitable type of microphone for sound level meters is the condenser microphone, which combines precision with stability and reliability (Hakala et al., 2010), Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sound level meter

The sound level meter can be used for measuring sound or noise for Community Noise Analysis. In the study entitled “The digital tester” Clark Roberts (2018) in their research, they created this for monitoring the noise. The objective of this invention aims to know the kind of noise. Some previous inventors in Author is Abioye Ayodeji Opeyemi, This Sound Pressure Level (SPL) represents the volume auditory perception, whose measuring device is known as decibel meter. According to David (isulat ang apilyedo sa mga authors then year) decibel meters are electroacoustic transducers capable of detecting sound and of converting it into an electrical signal, as well as of amplifying and processing it. According to the international standard IEC 616721(2002, such equipment

presents many variations, which directly affect its efficiency, accuracy and cost.

Numerical sound intensity values vary exponentially, thus, the magnitudes of the sensor’s electrical signals ranged from 100 to 2300 units, which, consequently, led to the great dispersion of these signals. Commercial decibel meters conventionally adopt the decibel unit, i.e. They use sound intensity values in a base -10 logarithmic scale (Halliday et al., 2012).

1.2 Solar energy

The use of the sun’s energy is nothing new and dates back to the beginning of time It is an essential source of renewable energy (Maka and Alabid, 2022). In recent years however, the focus on energy consumption worldwide rapidly spurred growth in the research and development of “green” alternative fuel source including the

sun, wind, hydro, wave, geothermal, hydrogen and other forms of energy. And today, because of that focus, the use of solar energy is expanding by leaps and bounds especially since sunlight is free, unlimited, readily available, clean and reliable. A solar power system is one which is capable of converting the absorbed sun energy; store it in a lead acid cell to be used on the load. In our part of the world, where power supply is not effective and efficient, the use of solar power supply is of immense value and advantage considering the fact that we are blessed or rich in sun light i.e. high degrees of temperatures which is the main thing that feeds a solar power supply unit for uses. It is low cost compared to other alternative sources of power supply in this society e.g. the use of generators which consume fuel or diesel and are really expensive, and its life span is better and reliable when used under or within or above the stipulated rating of the solar power device. Solar technologies are categorized as either passive or active depending on the way they capture, convert and distribute sunlight and enable solar energy to be harnessed at different levels around the world, mostly depending on the distance from the Equator, (Razak et al., 2016).

1.2.1 The Basics of Solar Power System Operation with Block Diagram

A typical solar power supply device is comprised of solar panel (a.k.a. photovoltaic or PV panels), a charge controller, a power inverter having a meter or monitoring system which is capable of monitoring voltages and system condition and the electrical distribution system. The basics of solar power system operation with block diagram is shown in Figure 2, (Bradford, 2006).

The solar panel absorbs energy produced by the sun and converts it into electrical energy precisely DC. It does this by absorbing the sun rays into the modules of the solar panel hence produced free electrical charge carriers in the conduction and valence bands. The photovoltaic panel comprised of silicon crystals, which reacts with sun ray and under this process, converts the sun rays into electricity. They supply the electricity for charging the batteries and for use by the appliances either directly or through an inverter. Multiple modules were used to produce more electricity and then any excess energy that was produced was stored in the batteries for use during the cloudy/ rainy weather. The panels are available in different sizes, voltages and amperage. They can be wired in series or in parallel depending on how the system is designed.

The electricity produced by the solar panel is then transferred to the charge controller. The charge controller regulates the rate at which electric current were drawn in and out of the battery. It turns off charge when the battery reaches the optimum charging point and turns it on when it goes below a certain level. It fully charges the battery without permitting overcharge. Solar charge controller is an electronic voltage regulator that is used to limit the rate at which electric current is being drawn in or out of the batteries. This charge controller turns off the charge when the battery reaches the optimum charging point and turns on when it goes below certain level. It fully charges the battery without permitting overcharge while preventing reverse current flow. Over voltage may reduce the battery performance or lifespan,

and may pose a safety risk. This charge controller shows system operation parameters, battery status and protection from over discharge. The charge controller is the brain behind the system. It monitors the electricity produced by the solar panel and then regulates the electricity that is used to charge the batteries and prevent them from becoming over charged. Proper charging is considered to prevent any damage to the batteries and thereby increasing the battery life and performance.

Solar battery is used in such projects. Without the battery, the system could only power when the sun is shining. The power would interrupt each time the cloud passes, the system would become very frustrating. The solar battery

provides constant electricity and the load discharges 80% of its charge. The batteries are the heart of the system and are available in different voltages and various amp-hour ratings depending on the requirement of the system.

The inverter converts the DC voltage produced by the solar panels (and from the energy stored in the batteries) into A C voltage. The inverter could also charge the batteries by using an alternative source such as the mains or generator connected to the inverter when they are available. Choosing the right inverter for the load demand and power requirements of the system is critical for the components to function properly.

Fig 2: Solar system block diagram

3.0 Materials and Method

3.1 Study Area

The study will be conducted at Delta State University, Oleh Campus, specifically within the Civil Engineering Department building. This one-storey structure houses various facilities, including classrooms, laboratories, and the Dean's office. The campus is located in a region characterized by frequent power outages,

leading to a heavy reliance on diesel generators for electricity supply. The environmental context includes both academic and administrative functions, making it essential to address noise pollution and explore sustainable energy alternatives.

3.2 Materials and Equipment

To achieve the objectives of this project, the following materials and equipment were utilized:

3.2.1 Noise measurement equipment

i. **Sound Level Meter:** A calibrated sound level meter was used to measure the noise levels generated by the diesel generators. This device provided accurate readings in decibels (dB) and helped identify peak noise times.

ii. **Data Logger:** A data logger may be employed to record noise levels over extended periods, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the noise environment.

3.2.2 Solar power system components

i. **Solar Panels:** Photovoltaic (PV) panels were evaluated for their capacity to meet the energy needs of the department. The distance (D) of separation between the panel and the battery was limited to 10 m in order to reduce the voltage drop along the cable from the solar panel since the solar panels are often mounted at some distance away from the battery in order to achieve maximum energy thus causing a distance of separation.

ii. **Inverters:** Inverters were used to convert the direct current (DC) generated by solar panels into alternating current (AC) for standard electrical appliances.

iii. **Batteries:** Energy storage solutions was considered to ensure a continuous power supply, especially during non-daylight hours.

iv. **Charge Controllers:** These devices will regulate the charging of batteries, preventing overcharging and optimizing the lifespan of the battery system.

3.2.3 noise mitigation materials

i. **Sound Barriers:** Various materials such as acoustic panels and sound-absorbing foam will be assessed for their effectiveness in reducing noise transmission.

ii. **Mufflers:** Mufflers will be analyzed for their potential to reduce noise emissions from generator exhausts.

3.3 Methods

3.3.1 Noise Assessment

i. **Site Visits (Recce.):** Conducted initial site visits to familiarize with the generators locations and operational patterns.

ii. **Noise Measurement:** Noise levels from electric generators were measured using a factory sound level meter (SLM), which was set at the slow response mode with A-weighting (A-weighted decibels or dBA). Measurements were conducted three times a day 8am-10am, 12pm-2pm, and 4pm-6pm in the indoor and outdoor environment at various locations around the Civil Engineering Department. **Noise Level Measurement:** Utilized the sound level meter to measure noise levels. The distances of each generator to one of the classrooms (BL 3) were measured and the combined noise level calculated using Equation 1. To calculate the combined noise level from multiple sources, we can use the formula for combining sound levels in decibels (dB):

$$L_{total} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n 10^{L_i/10} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where:

L_{total} = combined noise level,

L_i = individual noise level from each source.

The noise levels were first converted from dB to their linear scale, summed them up, and then converted back to dB.

Conversion of each noise level to linear scale:

For 41.5 dB: $10^{41.5/10} \approx 14125.38$

For 38.7 dB: $10^{38.7/10} \approx 738.42$

For 31.5 dB: $10^{31.5/10} \approx 141.25$

Sum the linear values:

$$Total = 14125.338 + 738.42 + 141.25 \approx 14895.05$$

Convert back to dB:

$$L_{total} = 10 \log_{10}(14895.05) \approx 10 \cdot 4.172 \approx 41.72 \text{ dB}$$

Thus, the combined noise level at the reference point is approximately 41.7 dB.

iii. Statistical Analysis: Data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16 at 5% level of significance. T-test was used to compare the means at the different time interval and identify times when noise levels exceed acceptable limits set by regulatory bodies (e.g., WHO guidelines).

3.2.2 Evaluation of Load And Power Consumption

Based on the table below, the electrical appliances to power were listed.

- i. The AC and DC systems were separated and entered in their appropriate table.
- ii. The operating watt of each load was recorded

iii. The number of hours per day for each item was specified.

iv. The operating wattage and the number of hours per day were multiplied out to determine the watt hour per day.

v. The total watt hour per week was determined by entering the number of days per week the load should be operated.

3.2.3 Power Consumption

There was need to determine the size of the load that were powered. The unit of measurement used was watt-Hour because it was applicable to both AC and DC circuits. The table below shows the average daily watt hours, the highest AC load in watts, the total AC connected wattage at a time, the total watt-hour per day, load

correction multiplying factor from page 15 and the corrected watt hour per day. These had allowed for easy determination of how many modules that were needed to produce the power required and how many batteries that were also needed to store the power. The table below was an analysis of energy usage for a representative of an office, the HOD’s office. The loads were

itemized for its individual run time per day and per week then summed the watt hour of all the units for a total daily watt hour figure. Table 1 helps for clear understanding of where the power had gone to and it also gave an idea of how to reduce the loads in the most effective manner when required.

Table 1: Load evaluation and power consumption table

Appliance	AC	DC	Qty	×	Wattage (volt × Amps) mult. by 1.15 for AC	×	Hrs per day	×	Hrs per week	/7	=	Avg. Watt hrs per day
Bulb	60		44	×	3,036	×	5	×	1	/7	=	2,168.
Fan	25		34	×	977.5	×	5	×	1	/7	=	698.2
Refrigerator	60		4	×	276	×	5	×	1	/7	=	197.1
Computer	40		29	×	1,334	×	5	×	1	/7	=	952.9
Photocopier	65		1	×	74.75	×	5	×	1	/7	=	53.4
Printer	40		1	×	46	×	5	×	1	/7	=	32.9
Television	40		1	×	184	×	5	×	1	/7	=	131.4
Highest AC loads in Watt	65W											
Σ	330W											3,610W
Total Watt-Hour per Day ÷ Load Correction Factor												3,610/70% = 5,157
Corrected Watt-Hour per Day					=	5,157Watt Hr/Day						

3.2.4 Battery sizing

This solar electric system was made up of a number of components and of these; none needs as much attention as the batteries. If batteries

are neglected, degradation will occur at a very fast pace. The battery sizing worksheet is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Battery Sizing Worksheet

S/N	Description	Calculation Description	Calculation	Result
1	To determine the watt-hour per day	It is taken from power consumption table		5,000W
2	The number of days of the storage required	Got from the approximation of number of cloudy days	3 chosen	3
3	Multiply 1 by line 2	5,000 x 3 (load wattage multiplied by 3)	5,000 x 3	15,000
4	Determine planned depth of discharge. 80% is the max. for lead deep cycle battery, 50% is a common amount for optimum longevity	Divide line 3 by 0.50	15,000/0.50	30,000
5	Derate your battery for low temperatures by multiplying line 4 by the factors below using lowest expected weekly average temperature	Multiply line 4 by the factor of 600 f which is equal 1.11 as the multiplier	30,000 x 1.11	33,300
6	Find the watt-hour capacity of your selected battery that is voltage times ampere hour capacity	48V x 150Amps Voltage x Amperage hour	48x150	7,200
7	Divide line 5 by line 6. The result is the number of batteries required	Divide line 5 by line 6	30,000/33,300	0.900
8	Round number of batteries to find system voltage. Where a 48 volts system require sets of 4 batteries	We are using a 12 volts system	0.900 is Approximate to 1	1

3.2.5 SOLAR PANEL SIZING

Accurately sizing the components of the solar electric system was important. This sizing helps ensure that the system produced the right amount of power that was required.

Typical PV electrical system types

There are two general types of electrical design for PV power systems for homes; systems that

interact with the utility power grid and had no battery backup capability and systems that interact and include battery back-up as well.

i. Grid Interactive only (NO battery backup): This type of system only operated when the utility was available. Since utility outages were rare, this system would normally provide the greatest amount of bill savings to the customers

***Agori John Ebipukebina, Okoroafor Solomon Ugwa, Oba Jeff and Umeadi Kester**

per charge cost of the investment. However, during the event of an outage, the system was required to shut down until utility power was restored.

ii. Stand-alone power system: For this project, a stand-alone power system was chosen for design and installation. First there was need to consider the electricity needs which the PV system had to power, the unit measurement was in kilo watts for consideration. Solar panels are classified according to their rated power output in watts. This rating was the amount of power the solar panel was be expected to produce in one peak sun hour. Different geographical locations received different quantities of average peak sun

hour per day. Solar panels could be wired in series or in increase voltage or current respectively. The rated terminal voltage of a 12 volts solar panel were usually around 17.0 volts, but through the use of a regulator, this voltage was reduced to around 13 to 15 volts as required for battery charging. To size the solar panel, how much power each items consumed while operating was determined. Most appliances had a label on the back, which listed the wattage and specification sheets, local appliance dealers and the product manufacturers were the sources of the information.

Solar Array Sizing worksheet

Table 3 presents Solar Array Sizing worksheet

Table 3; Solar Array Sizing worksheet

S/N	Solar Array Sizing Worksheet	Yearly Average
1	The site for mounting was located and the isolation sun penetration value was chosen as 5	6
2	The daily corrected loads in watt hour from the load calculation sheet was taken as	5,000
3	The corrected load value divided by the sun isolation penetration value was the number of watt needed to be generated per hour.	833.33
4	The actual power produced by the selected module GP 64's had each module produce 3.66amps. 57 volts which was a common charging voltage for a 48volt system, hence actual power = amperage × charging voltage.	57 x 3.66 = 208.62W
5	The value of the generated power per hour divided by the actual power produced by the selected module, the result was the number of module required for the system. When rounding this number, 12 sets of 600w each panel to be connected in 4 series. Module were needed for the 48 volts system.	12

3.3 INSTALLATION

Basic steps that were followed while installing the PV system

i. It was ensured that the roof area for installation was capable of handling the system area or size.

ii. It was ensured that there were no roof penetrations that needed roofing industry approved sealing methods.

iii. The PV system was installed according to the manufacturer specifications, using installation requirements such as the right wire gauge, nuts and bolts from the manufacturers' specification.

iv. The PV system was properly grounded with the system parts to reduce the threat of shock hazard induced surges.

v. It was ensured that the right wire with the right polarity was observed while connecting the solar panel to the charge controller.

vi. It was ensured that the design met local utility interconnection requirement.

vii. The solar panel was set placed under the sun at 45° south, there the peak sun irradiation was on the panel surface and then at 39.5 volts was observed using a multimeter.

viii. While observing the voltage, the panel was slightly adjusted and the voltage varied at an angle away from the sun, the voltage depreciated

ix. The output from the solar panel was connected to the charge controller with respect to their polarities and when the output voltage was observed, it then read 57 volts which was right for charging 48 volts battery, since the FOUR 12 volts batteries were connected in series.

x. Also there was an indicator on the charge controller that showed when the battery was full by

xi. Showing green light and the other LED showed red when load was connected to the system.

xii. It was finally inspected for completion by the HOD of Civil Engineering Department.

3.3.1 Evaluation of the Noise Level after Installation of the Solar System

The noise level from the other two generators were reevaluated to know the noise level in the absence of the third generator.

To calculate the combined noise level from multiple sources, we can use the formula for combining

sound levels in decibels (dB).

Conversion of each noise level to linear scale:

For 38.7 dB: $10^{38.7/10} \approx 738.42$

For 31.5 dB: $10^{31.5/10} \approx 141.25$

Sum the linear values:

$Total = 738.42 + 141.25 \approx 879.67$

Convert back to dB:

$L_{total} = 10 \log_{10}(879.6775) \approx 10 \times 2.94$
 $\approx 29.4 \text{ dB}$

Thus, the combined noise level at the reference point is approximately 29.4 dB. This value is below the WHO standard.

xii. Statistical Analysis: Data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16 at 5% level of significance. T-test was used to compare the means at the different time interval and identify times when noise levels exceed acceptable limits set by regulatory bodies (e.g., WHO guidelines).

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Noise level from generators

The results of the noise level of each of the generators and their distances are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Noise level

Location of generator	Noise level (dB) at source	Distance from classroom (m)	Noise level (dB) at classroom	Combined noise level $L_{total} = 10\log_{10}(\sum_{i=1}^n 10^{L_i/10})$
Civil Engineering	80.0	24.3	41.5	41.72dB
Chemical Engineering	63.0	37.8	38.7	
Dean's office	58.0	31.7	31.5	

41.72 dB is above the ideal noise level of 35dB in classrooms/libraries for optimal learning (Shield and Dockrell, 2008).

4.1.2: Solar System

Each battery read 12.8 volts each and then connected in series to give an output of 48 volts afterwards was connected to the inverter. The voltage was 57 volts DC because the solar and the charge controller were also connected but without load, then load was added to the inverter which gave an output of 220 volts and was left for about 30 minutes after then it was observed again and the voltage did not vary. The inverter had three indicators. The first displayed if the system was connected to the mains or not, the second displayed if the inverter system was switched ON or OFF and the third was to display if the system was experiencing any fault or not. The inverter also had an additional socket for plugging the inverter to mains to serves as

another means to charge the batteries other than the solar system. When tested with the volt meter as it was plugged on the mains out, it read 14.4 volts which was basically because of the state of the charge level of the batteries. The batteries would normally self-discharge over time even when not used. Since the inverter included a triple cycle charger, it could continue to maintain the battery with equalization charge voltage of about 12 volts just to make sure that the battery does not discharge even it was on standby mode. Table 5 shows the various capacities and quantities of the solar energy components.

Table 5: Solar energy components

S/N	Component	Battery	Quantity
1	Sola panel	600W	12
2	Battery	12.8V	4
3	Inverter	5000W	1
4	Charge controller		1
5	Cables and connectors		

4.1.3 Noise Reduction

The use of solar system in the Civil Engineering Department has reduced the noise level from 41.72dB to 29.4 dB, which is far below the WHO recommended standard in academic environment.

5.0 Conclusion

The project was intended to supply 5000 watts of energy to the office of the Civil Engineering Department. The noise level estimates in the building both in the indoor and outdoor environment at the different time interval exceeded the World Health Organization (WHO) limits and most of the students spend more than 6 hours a day at school. The WHO guideline set the maximum noise levels in classrooms and outdoor playgrounds at 35dB and 55dB respectively (WHO, 1999). During the design of the system requirement, it was considered to adjust the wattage of the inverter from 200 watts to 1500 watts inverter system due to an expected future expansion of the load capacity. Another change that had occurred during the design was the change from 12 volts solar panel to 48 volts solar panel and from 24volts battery to an additional one more battery, which then became a 57 volts system to fit the solar panel that was already purchased. Solar panel with inverter is a noiseless source of energy, it does not use fuel

and it is environmentally friendly. It is a convenient way of producing an alternative means of power supply to supplement the mains failure. It is advantageous to user who could afford its initial cost of installation. This project is recommended for expansion if the need arose. There would be need to add up more batteries to meet up with the running time and the system load capacity since the system had an adjusted wattage, more load could be added only with addition of more batteries to meet up with the capacity.

Competing interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable

Funding

The research was self-funded by the authors

Authors' contribution

JEA conceived, designed and coordinated the research and drafted the template for the manuscript, KE took measurements of sound levels and took record of electrical appliances, JO and SUO both evaluated the power

consumption and sizing of the solar components.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratitude to the Head of Civil and Environmental Engineering

REFERENCES

Agaja, T.M. and Akande, G. P. (2024). Impact of Noise Pollution on The Academic Performance of Students in The University of Ilorin's Learning Environment, Nigeria. FUDMA Journal of Earth and Environmental Sciences (FUDJEES), 1(2), 42-57.

Agbo, C.O.A. (2020). Noise Pollution in Nigeria's Institutions of Higher Learning: A Review Journal of Engineering Research and Reports, 18(1): 8-21.

Bradford, T. (2006). Solar Revolution: The Economic Transformation of the Global Energy Industry, Boston: MIT Press.

Bulunuz, N. (2014). Noise Pollution in Turkish elementary schools: Evaluation of noise pollution awareness and sensitivity training. International Journal of Environmental and science Education, 9, 215- 234.

Camarilloa, M. E. C., Sangalangb, G.D., Pantinoplec, H.L. and Batocoyd, M.O. (2021). Assessment of Noise Pollution Exposure to Elementary Students: A Case in Argao, Cebu, Philippines. International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR), 60(4), 331- 344

Department Engr. Dr. J.E Agori and the Dean of the Faculty of Engineering, Engr. Prof K.M. Oghenejabor.

Chen, L., Wang, Y., & Zhang, T. (2022). Economic analysis of solar energy systems in academic institutions. Renewable Energy, 178, 1234-1242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.12.045>

Diaco, S. B. (2014). Effects of Noise Pollution in the Learning Environment on Cognitive Performances. Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research, 10(1).

Federal Republic of Nigeria (NESREA), Official Gazette, National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act, 2007, National Environmental (Noise Standards And Control) Regulations 2009, No.67, Vol.96 Abuja, Federal Government Printer, Lagos, Nigeria. FGP112/102009/1,000(OL60);2009.

Ghaffarian, A. H., Dahlan, N. D., Ali, U.B. (2013). Sustainable energy performances of green buildings: A review of current theories, implementations and challenges. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 25, 1-17

Hakala, I.; Kivela, I.; Ihalainen, J.; Luomala, J.; Gao, C. (2010). Design of Low-Cost Noise Measurement Sensor Network: Sensor

- Function Design. In Proceedings of the 2010 First International Conference on Sensor Device Technologies and Applications, Venice, Italy, 18–25 July 2010; pp. 172–179
- Halliday L. F., Taylor J. L., Millward K. E., Moore D. R. (2012). Lack of generalization of auditory learning in typically developing children. *J. Speech Lang. Hear. Res.* 55 168–181
- Hatice, M. B. and Filiz, B. K. (2022) Analysis of different methods of suppressing generator noise reaching indoor noise. *The European Physical Journal E* 6(3):161-178
- Iorbee, M.M, Yaaya, A.D. and Myem, S.T. (2017). Impact of Solar Power System on Academic Performance of Science and Technical College Students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. *International Journal of Educational Research and Management Technology (IJERMT)*, 2(3), 2545-5877.
- Maka, A. O. M. and Alabid, J. I. M. (2022). "Solar energy technology and its roles in sustainable development". *Clean Energy*. 6 (3): 476–483.
- Mark, P.C. Paul Covita (2018). Design and Development of Noise Meter and Automatic Alarm for Sound Intensity Level *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology* 6(5):40-53
- Nathan, D and Abioye A. O. (2013). Solar Power System: A Viable Renewable Energy Source for Nigeria. *Quest Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering Research (JECER)* 1 (1), 10-19.
- Olamijulo, J. (2016). Noise from Portable Electric Power Generators in an Institutional Setting: A Neglected Risk Factor. *International Journal of Environmental Monitoring and Analysis*. 4(4). 115 - 120.
- Olamijulo, J.O., Godson, Rowland, G. A, Oyewale M. M. (2016). Noise from Portable Electric Power Generators in an Institutional Setting: A Neglected Risk Factor *International Journal of Environmental Monitoring and Analysis*, 4(4):115 - 120
- Pratama, X.G, Dhea, R,A, Alissa, N., , R.F. and Arrayyan, M.Z (2023). Implementation and Feasibility Study of Solar-powered Streetlighting Systems in Rural Community Area 425(3).
- Razak A., Irwan Y.M., Leow W.Z., Irwanto M., Safwati I., Zhafarina M. (2016). Investigation of the effect temperature on photovoltaic (PV) panel output performance. *Int. J. Adv. Sci. Eng. Inf. Technol.*, 6 (682)
- Shied, B. M. and Dockrell, J. E. (2008). The effect of environmental and classroom noise on the academic attainments of primary school children. *The journal of the*

Acoustical society of America, 123(1), 133 - 144.

Smith, L. R, Radestsky, A. L., and Yue, L (2010). Pattern to daylight schools for people and sustainability. Lighting research center-Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute. Retrieved July 12th, 2017 from www.Irc.rpi.edu > daylighting.

Standards and Control) Regulations 2009, No. 67, Vol. 96 Abuja, Federal Government Printer, Lagos, Nigeria. FGP112/102009/1,000(OL60);2009.

Vassiliades, C. gathokleous,R. Barone, G. Forzano, C et al., (2022). Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. Building integration of active solar energy systems: A review of geometrical and architectural characteristics

WHO (World Health Organisation). (1999) Guidelines for Community Noise. <http://www.who.int/peh/>

Yang, D. Wang, N W, Gueymard, C, A., Tao H., Jan Kleissl, J.H. Marc J. Perez, R.P, Jamie, M. Bright, X., Xia, Meer, D.Vand Ian M.P, (2022), A review of solar forecasting, its dependence on atmospheric sciences and implications for grid integration: Towards carbon neutrality, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews,Volume (6)